

RECENT HERBAL TREATMENT FOR POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME (PCOS) 2021-2022 ON LETROZOLE INDUCED MODEL: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a complex and heterogeneous condition that can affect females of reproductive age, which has a variety of symptoms. Women with PCOS frequently experience endocrine and metabolic problems like infertility, obesity, type 2 diabetes, hyperandrogenism and elevated luteinizing hormone (LH).

Objective: This review showed the effectiveness of herbal compounds and phytoconstituents for PCOS healing.

Materials and Methods: In this review, we investigate herbal compounds, phytoconstituents, and their therapeutic uses against PCOS using Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar published in 2021-2022. For this review, we used search terms like "herbal treatment," "phytotherapy," "letrozole," and "PCOS."

Results: This review identified 32 pertinent studies from 2021-2022, which were briefly described. The most reliable herbal remedies for PCOS in animal models were used to treat anomalies in glucose and estrous cycles, lipid profiles, cardiovascular parameters, steroidogenic enzymes, and serum hormonal profiles. **Conclusion:** This review claims that herbal extracts and phytoconstituents reduce hyperandrogenism, insulin resistance and ovarian weight while also increasing ovulation. Therefore, these plants and phytoconstituents may be relatively beneficial in treating this condition, offering a chance to research and develop new herbal remedies in the future.

Key Words: Herbal treatment, Phytotherapy, Letrozole, and PCOS.

Introduction

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), the most frequent endocrine disorder affecting women, manifests as a variety of phenotypes, including changes in the reproductive, endocrine, and metabolic systems⁽¹⁾. 70–80% of women with PCOS experience infertility because the disorder can interrupt ovulation and cause it to stop. Further, PCOS has been associated with a higher risk of miscarriage, anxiety, and melanchol⁽²⁾ ⁽³⁾. Menstrual irregularities, anovulation, amenorrhea, hirsutism, and infertility are the hallmarks of PCOS⁽⁴⁾. Additionally, numerous clinical and metabolic complications have been documented, including insulin resistance and diabetes, obesity, severe coronary artery disease, hypertension, endometrial hyperplasia, and ovarian and breast malignancies⁽⁵⁾. Hyperinsulinemia causes disruptions in the absorption and utilisation of glucose and prolongs anovulation by releasing higher quantities of testosterone and luteinizing hormone⁽⁶⁾. In 2012, 116 million women worldwide were affected by PCOS (4%–12%), according to the World Health Organization (WHO), and by 2020, that number had sharply climbed to 26%.⁽⁷⁾ PCOS prevalence in India ranges from 3.7 to 22.5%, depending on the population studied and the diagnostic criteria used⁽⁸⁾. Allopathic medications such clomiphene citrate, metformin, tamoxifen, and troglitazone are currently the most widely used to manage the PCOS⁽⁹⁾. Those are having numerous side effects such as Hot flashes, arthritis, joint or muscle discomfort, as well as psychological side effects like impatience, mood swings, sadness, and bloating⁽¹⁰⁾. So, it is important to find and develop alternative medications due to the negative effects of these medications. Recently, attention has been drawn to herbal PCOS remedies as a way of managing the lifestyle that can help to regain control of both the menstrual cycle and normal blood hormone levels⁽¹¹⁾. In contrast, several preclinical PCOS investigations have been conducted, including those involving androgen excess, Dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA), and estradiol valerate. A PCOS model created by

letrozole, a non-steroidal aromatase inhibitor, resembles human PCOS in many aspects. Endogenous hyperandrogenism has been induced using letrozole, a nonsteroidal aromatase inhibitor⁽¹²⁾.Letrozole alters the estrous cycle in female rats and makes the ovaries heavier. These ovaries have many cysts, thin granulosa cell layers, thickening theca cell layers, and atretic follicles ^{(13) (14) (15)}. Infusing female rats with letrozole at modest doses over time might cause PCOS-like metabolic and reproductive characteristics⁽¹⁶⁾. Women from metropolitan cities mainly affected by PCOS due to sedentary lifestyle. Whereas treatment is symptomatic so, there is need to address issue related presently suffering PCOS woman hence, herbal compound may pay crucial role in treatment of PCOS. In this article, we are going to address the pathophysiology, aetiology and impacts of various herbal extracts on PCOS that were published in year 2021-22.

Pathophysiology Of PCOS⁽¹⁷⁾

Fig No.1- Pathophysiology Of PCOS.

Changes in food, lifestyle, and exposure to specific environmental contaminants can all have a negative impact on a woman with PCOS. One of the neuro-endocrine features of PCOS is

an increase in luteinizing hormone (LH) serum levels, a greater LH/FSH ratio, and an increase in the amplitude and frequency of LH secretion. The hormonal imbalance that affects follicular growth during the ovarian cycle causes the injured follicle to remain in the ovary. Every menstrual cycle produces a new cyst, thus the imprisoned follicle develops into one, resulting in several ovarian cysts. Women with PCOS typically suffer insulin resistance because of their increased weight. In order to overcome this resistance, the body secretes more insulin, which leads to a hyperinsulinemic state. They are all indications of type 2 diabetes. Another reason causing greater amounts of testosterone is high insulin levels, which cause a decline in circulating sex hormone-binding globulin levels (SHBG). As a result, free testosterone levels increase and hyperandrogenism's characteristic signs and symptoms worsen. Elevated androgen levels in the ovary have an effect on the follicle as it matures during the ovarian cycle, which causes the particular follicle to anovulate.

Causes of PCOS

In comparison to the estimated 4-6% prevalence in the general population, approximately 20–40% of first-degree female relatives of women with PCOS go on to get the condition themselves⁽¹⁸⁾. Different causes of PCOS are⁽¹⁹⁾:

- Personality
- Increased level of insulin
- Genetic inclination
- Periods of disruption
- Estrogen level
- androgen level
- Hormonal imbalance
- Unhealthy food

- Inflammation
- Environmental factors

Signs and symptoms of PCOS⁽⁷⁾

Fig No.2- Signs and symptoms of PCOS.

Phenotype⁽²⁰⁾

Phenotypes are a person's distinguishable characteristics. Women with PCOS can have all three of the following phenotypes: high androgen levels (HA), ovarian dysfunction (OD), and polycystic ovarian morphology (POM).

Fig No.3- Phenotypes of PCOS.

Type D is the least severe form, whereas type A is the most severe. A and C phenotypes are the most prevalent⁽²¹⁾.

Complications associated with PCOS⁽⁷⁾

1. Obesity
2. Type II diabetes
3. Endometrial carcinoma
4. Cardiovascular disorder
5. Metabolic syndrome

Criteria for diagnose PCOS⁽⁸⁾

1. NIH (National Institute of Health)/NICHD (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development)-
 - The process of oligo ovulation.
 - Signs of excess androgen (clinical or biochemical).
 - The presence of extra testosterone and other disorders that can affect menstruation have been ruled out.

Both requirements 1 and 2 must be satisfied.

2. ESHRE (European Society for Human Reproduction) and Embryology/ASRM (American Society of Reproductive Medicine)-
 - ovarian an ovulations or oligo ovulation.
 - An excessive synthesis of androgen.
 - Polycystic ovarian syndrome, as detected by gynecologic ultrasound, which shows 12 follicles and 2–9 mm in each ovary.

Two of the three requirements must be fulfilled.

3. AE-PCOS (Androgen Excess and PCOS Society)-

- An excessive synthesis of testosterone.
- Oligo-or anovulatory cycles or polycystic ovary.
- Every other substance that might boost androgen activity has been ruled out.

Conditions 1 and 2 must both be fulfilled.

Management of PCOS

Presently, only symptomatic treatment is available for polycystic ovary syndrome. The goal of the medically prescribed drug is to only manage PCOS symptoms⁽²²⁾. The most popular PCOS therapies now include allopathic drugs including clomiphene citrate, metformin, tamoxifen, and troglitazone⁽⁹⁾. Allopathic medications frequently have negative side effects such as hot flashes, arthritis, joint or muscle pain, and adverse psychological consequences like impatience, alterations in mood, melancholy and bloating⁽¹⁰⁾. There are numerous excellent herbal medicines used in traditional herbal therapy that have the ability to treat and prevent PCOS⁽²³⁾. Herbal treatments for PCOS have recently attracted attention as a method of lifestyle management where the menstrual cycle and normal blood hormone levels can be restored⁽¹¹⁾. Herbal therapies have been demonstrated to improve insulin sensitivity, standardise menstrual cycles, reduce polycystic ovaries and ovarian volume, increase FSH and 17-estradiol levels, and reduce testosterone levels⁽²⁴⁾.

This review gives an insight into the effect of different herbal plants and phytoconstituents on letrozole-induced PCOS.

Materials and methods

In this review, by using the Scopus, PubMed, Google Scholar, we explore the herbal compounds, phytoconstituents and their therapeutic applications against PCOS.

We utilised relevant keywords to search like "herbal treatment," "phytotherapy," "letrozole," and "PCOS" for this review. Only publications that were released between 2021 and 2022 used to give insight of beneficial effect of herbal compounds in PCOS. We looked through all study that how herbal extracts and different phytoconstituents work on PCOS that involved animals. After testing herbal remedies on animals, 32 studies were finally chosen.

Results

Numerous studies have been conducted on PCOS and its traditional herbal remedies. These treatments all have various outcomes. Following the induction of PCOS with letrozole, use of several herbal extracts during therapy and phytoconstituents reduces blood testosterone and LH levels while increasing progesterone and FSH levels. Many follicles were also observed in the treatment group at various stages of growth.

On the basis of recent studies, the majority of the herbal extract and phytoconstituents are capable of bringing blood hormone levels back to normal and are successful in treating PCOS, disappearance of cyst, able to reduce insulin resistance, reduce both the body and ovarian weight, regulation of estrous cycle, ameliorate lipid profile and other PCOS symptoms. Further, due to the presence of phytoestrogens, which are weak antagonists of oestrogen and exhibit more potent estrogenic effects when the body's oestrogen level is low in PCOS patients. Medicinal plants used for the treatment of PCOS have no significant side effects and can therefore be used widely.

Different herbal compounds and phytoconstituents were also showed beneficial effect in PCOS are described below:

Herbal plants

- 1. Sara E. Ali et al, 2021^[25]: Cicer arietinum L. (phytoestrogen)** pre-clinical study in the dose 250-500mg/kg for 28 days resulting
 - The ovarian weight was greatly reduced, but it had no impact on the uterine weight.
 - A reduction in the quantity and size of cystic follicles.
 - Granulosa cell thickness increased, whereas theca cell thickness decreased significantly.
 - In the treatment groups, hormone levels, metabolic condition and antioxidant status were all enhanced.
 - Cyp11a1 mRNA expression was markedly reduced.
- 2. Firdaus Kausar et al, 2021⁽²⁶⁾: Cuscuta reflexa and Peucedanum grande** pre-clinical study in the dose [CRE-112mg/kg, PGE-28mg/kg] for 21 days resulting
 - The ovarian weight was greatly reduced, but it had no impact on the uterine weight.
 - A reduction in the quantity and size of cystic follicles.
 - Granulosa cell thickness increased, whereas theca cell thickness decreased significantly.
 - In the treatment groups, hormone levels, metabolic condition and antioxidant status were all enhanced.
 - Cyp11a1 mRNA expression was markedly reduced.
- 3. Mona Mohamed Abd El-Galil et al, 2021^[27]: Flaxseed (Phytoestrogen)** pre-clinical study in the dose [500 mg/kg] for 4 weeks resulting
 - Final BW and ovarian weight both significantly decreased after flaxseed treatment.

- Following administration of flaxseed extract, decrease in blood glucose levels was observed and also showed a significant reduction in MDA and TNF- α
 - Considerably reduced levels of T and LH and significantly elevated levels of oestrogen and progesterone were observed.
 - Treatment group displayed typical cyclical changes, a large rise in average amount of corpora lutea and developing follicles in addition a considerable reduction in the average number of cystic follicles.
- 4. Niknaz Moradi et al, 2021⁽²⁸⁾: Korean red ginseng (Phytoestrogen)** pre-clinical study in the dose [100 mg/kg] for 14 days resulting
- In PCOS rats, KRGE alone or in combination with oral contraceptives effectively normalised weight of ovaries, reduced LH serum levels and eliminated the cysts in the ovary.
 - KRGF showed reduction in testosterone and NF- κ B levels.
- 5. SK Bhoje et al, 2021⁽²⁹⁾: Aloe vera gel and mint tea (Phytoestrogen)** pre-clinical study in the dose [Aloe vera gel-1ml Mint tea-ad-lib] for 30 days resulting
- Restored ovarian structure, hormonal levels, and oestrus cyclicity, showing the most positive results.
- 6. Muhammad Alif Haslan et al, 2021⁽³⁰⁾: Ficus deltoidei** pre-clinical study in the dose [250,500 and 1000mg/kg] for 15 days resulting
- In PCOS rats, treatment with *F. deltoidea* brought down levels of T, LH, FSH, malondialdehyde (MDA), insulin resistance, obesity, total cholesterol, triglycerides and low-density lipoprotein (LDL).
 - The levels of superoxide dismutase (SOD), oestrogen, and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL) are unchanged.

- Histopathological study showed that *F. deltoidea* enhanced the quantity of corpus luteum and the thickness of the endometrium.
- 7. Asmaa A. Azouz et al, 2021⁽³¹⁾: *Actaea racemosa* and vitamin C** pre-clinical study in the dose [AR extract-7.14 mg/kg Vit.C-500 mg/kg] for 28 days resulting
- After treatment, all groups experienced a decrease in relative ovarian and uterine weight.
 - LH and testosterone levels were significantly decreased.
 - Normal MDA and GSH levels were restored by AR extract with and without vitamin C.
 - Significantly reduced ALT and AST activity were observed in the vitamin C and to a lower degree in the combination group.
 - The combination of AR and vitamin C was successful in correcting the PCOS rat's dysregulated levels of testosterone, luteinizing hormone, and Cyp191 gene mRNA.
- 8. Swati B. Pokale*, Dr. Ghanshayam Jadhav, 2021⁽³²⁾: *Piper longum* (Linn.) (Phytoestrogen)** pre-clinical study in the dose [200, 400 and 800 mg/kg] for 35days resulting
- Regulation of estrous cycle.
 - Rat ovary and reproductive weights that are restored to normal following treatment with plant drugs.
- 9. Thirumurugan Ayyadurai et al, 2021^[33]: *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb** pre-clinical study in the dose [100, 200 and 300 mg/kg] for 28 days resulting
- Decreased level of total cholesterol, LDL, VLDL, and triacylglyceride levels, together with an increased (HDL).
 - Testosterone levels were dropped, progesterone and oestrogen levels were increased

- Displayed healthy follicles at various growth stages and the corpus luteum along with healthy endometrial glands, luminal epithelial cells, and stroma with blood arteries.

10. Meng-fan Peng et al,2021⁽³⁴⁾: *Eucommia ulmoides* Olive leaves pre-clinical study in the dose [220, 110 and 55 mg/kg] for a 21days resulting

- TFEL decreased BW, the Lee's index, the ovarian index, the ovarian area and the ovarian volume. It also boosted serum E2, SHBG levels, and ISI, decreased serum levels of T, LEP, INS, and FBG and decreased the HOMA-IR.
- In rats with PCOS-IR, treatment with TFEL decreased the levels of Kiss1, IGF-1 and AR in the arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus, increased the levels of Kiss1, decreased IGF-1, and AR in the pituitary gland, and decreased the levels of IGF-1, LEPR, and AR in the ovary.
- TFEL was able to promote IRS-1, p-IRS-1Tyr895, PI3Kp85, p-PI3Kp85, AKT, and p-AKT in the ovary and ameliorate histological alterations in ovary and pancreas.

11. Sudhakar Pachiappan et al, 2021⁽³⁵⁾: *Gymnema sylvestre* and *Pergularia daemia* pre-clinical study in the dose [G. sylvestre-100mg/kg P. daemia-300 mg/kg] for 28 days resulting

- Combining G. sylvestre and P. daemia treatments resulted in a longer-lasting regularisation of estrus cycle duration than either treatment alone.
- When compared to the treatment group (alone), the G. sylvestre and P. daemia treatment combination demonstrated quantitatively greater reduction of hyperglycemia
- Combination treatment with produced the best improvement in the changed lipid profile and also reversed the hormonal irregularity.
- Significantly reduced the weights of the ovary and uterus.

- Showed the presence of the corpus luteum healthy normal follicles as well as the least amount of cysts and an antrum that was less fluid-filled.

12. NOREEN ANWAR et al, 2021⁽³⁶⁾: Nigella Sativa seed and oil pre-clinical study in the dose [Seed powder-10 g/kg Oil-4ml/kg] for 56 days resulting

After receiving therapy with *Nigella sativa*, it was discovered that body weight, weight and ovarian volume had decreased to normal levels.

13. Mohd Zahoor ul Haq shah et al, 2022⁽³⁷⁾: Turmeric extract (Phytoestrogen) pre-clinical study in the dose [175 mg/kg] for 30 days resulting

- Displayed a loss of body weight.
- Produced the best improvement in the changed lipid profile and also reversed the hormonal irregularity.
- Treatment with turmeric extract lowers plasma IL-6 levels and increases the amount of circulating adiponectin.
- Significantly increased the activity of SOD and GSH while reducing MDA levels.

14. Ahmed A. Morsi et al, 2022⁽³⁸⁾: Stevia Leaf pre-clinical study in the dose [300 mg/kg] for 7 days resulting

- Restored the natural vaginal cyclicity and displayed improved body weight management.
- Produced the best improvement in the changed lipid profile and also reversed the hormonal irregularity.
- Reduced insulin resistance and blood sugar levels.
- MDA and TNF- levels were dramatically reduced, whereas SOD levels were significantly raised.

- Displayed improvement in the thickness of the granulosa and theca cell layers, restoration of follicular development, and an increase in the mature follicles and corpora lutea.
- Revealed that the corpora lutea and ovarian follicle granulosa cells had higher levels of TGF- expression.

15. Femi-Olabisi Fehintoluwa Joy et al, 2022⁽³⁹⁾: *Ocimum gratissimum* (Linn.) Leaves pre-clinical study in the dose [0.5ml and 1ml] for 21 days resulting

- Albumin concentration increased for 50mg/kg and decreased for 100 mg/kg of extract.
- The concentration of globulin and total protein significantly increased. And the concentration of direct bilirubin significantly dropped.
- The concentration of total bilirubin significantly increased at 100 mg/kg and decreased at 50 mg/kg of extract.
- Creatinine concentration significantly increased for extracts at 50 mg/kg and significantly decreased for extracts at 100 mg/kg.
- Both the blood urea nitrogen-creatinine ratio and uric acid content significantly increased.
- Rats given a 50mg/kg extract orally showed a significantly decreased in aspartate aminotransferase activity in the liver and serum, whereas rats given a 100mg/kg extract showed a significant increase in activity.
- The serum level of alkaline phosphatase increased significantly while that in the liver reduced significantly.
- For 50mg/kg of the extract, alanine aminotransferase activity significantly decreased in serum and increased in the liver, whereas for 100mg/kg of the extract, it significantly increased in serum and decreased in the liver.

16. Liaqat Hussain et al, 2022⁽⁴⁰⁾: BitterMelon (*Momordica charantia* L.)(Phytoestrogen)

pre-clinical study in the dose [500 mg/kg] for 21 days resulting

- Histopathological examination of the ovaries showed growing and mature follicles.
- A significant decrease in LH surge, insulin, and testosterone levels, as well as an increase in FSH levels, were found in a hormone analysis.
- Significant improvements were also found in the lipid profile and antioxidant enzyme status.

17. Anam Younas et al, 2022⁽⁴¹⁾: Fagonia indica pre-clinical study in the dose [500 mg/kg]

for 7 weeks resulting

- Showed decreased BW, cleared ovarian cysts, and promoted follicular expansion.
- Boosted the production of antioxidant enzymes.

There is a non-significant increase in HDL and a significant drop in cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL

18. Sunday A Adelokun et al, 2022⁽⁴²⁾: Cyperus esculentus tubers pre-clinical study in

the dose [500 mg/kg] for 30 days resulting

- Brings the diestrous dominant cycle back to being steady and normal.
- There were lower concentrations of testosterone, LH, and cystic follicles, but higher concentrations of estradiol, progesterone, and antimullerian hormone.
- Final body and ovarian weight were decreased.
- Increased activity of ovarian COX-1 concentration while decreased activity of ovarian COX-2.
- Reduce the amount of MDA and increase the amount of GSH, indicating the antioxidant, and also significantly raise the amount of ovarian TP, SOD and CAT.

19. Hyun Yang et al, 2022⁽⁴³⁾: D-Chiro-Inositol and Ecklonia cava K pre-clinical study in the dose [EC - 250mg/kg and DCI - 50 mg/kg] for 2 weeks resulting

- EC and DCI regulate the estrous cycle and prevented the peritoneal posterior fat from expanding. They had no effect on weight.
- Level of T and LH were found to be lowered and increased level of E2.
- TNF and IL-6 levels, were significantly reduced.
- Kitl and Has mRNA expression levels showed increased levels.
- The thicknesses of the theca and granulosa cells have been normalised. The group receiving EC and DCI showed less cystic follicles and appearance of mature follicles.
- Treatment group showed the highest levels of LHR and FSHR mRNA expression.
- PPAR- γ and anti-inflammatory cytokine expression levels were restored.

20. Datu Agasi Mohd Kamal et al, 2022⁽⁴⁴⁾: Kelulut Honey pre-clinical study in the dose [0.5,1 or 2 g/kg/day] for 35 days resulting

- After treatment with all three doses of Kelulut honey, there is no significant drop in blood glucose level.
- Kelulut honey treatment had no effect on the body weight.
- Kelulut honey (1 g/kg/day) improved cystic follicles, raised corpus luteum and antral follicle counts, and normalised the oestrus cycle.

21. Amir Shieh et al, 2022⁽⁴⁵⁾: Ferula assa-foetida oleo-gum resin (phytoestrogen) pre-clinical study in the dose [12.5, 25, and 50 mg/kg] for 2 weeks resulting

- Showed less weight gain and there was no any change was observed in the levels of urea, creatinine, AST, ALT, ALP, or LDH.

- Significantly lowered the serum testosterone level than the PCOS group and also increased the thickness of the theca cell layer, number of corpora lutea and antral follicles in the ovarian region.
- Significantly higher levels of LHR, AMPK, adiponectin, and adiponectin receptor 1 and 2 expression were observed. The CYP11A1 gene's expression was significantly reduced.

Phytoconstituents

1. **Aynaz Mihanfar et al, 2021⁽⁴⁶⁾: Quercetin** (phytoestrogen) pre-clinical study in the dose of [100 mg/kg] for 30 days resulting
 - Improved lipid profile, progesterone, estradiol, and testosterone levels in the serum, as well as improved IR disturbances.
 - Ovarian tissue showed increased expression of AMPK and SIRT-1.
 - Quercetin also corrected the alteration in adiponectin, visfatin & resistin levels in adipose tissue.
2. **Jia Yu et al, 2021⁽⁴⁷⁾: Berberine** pre-clinical study in the dose of [95 & 190 mg/kg] for 4 weeks resulting
 - Displayed significant reductions in the levels of FPG, FINS & HOMA-IR.
 - Restored the serum hormone levels.
 - The administration of berberine showed follicles in various stages of development, enlarged corpora lutea, radiated oocyte & corona in mature follicle & thickened the granulosa cell layer.
 - Berberine exhibited proliferative & anti-apoptotic effects on granulosa cells as well as an inhibition of apoptosis in ovarian tissue cells.
 - Showed disruption of the PI3K/AKT pathway.
3. **Sasan Amanat et al, 2021⁽⁴⁸⁾: Genistein** (phytoestrogen) pre-clinical study in the dose of [20 mg/kg] for 42 days resulting
 - BW and ovarian weight were reduced.
 - Displayed a notable increase in SOD activity while maintaining TAC. In HOMA-IR, no significant rise was seen.
 - The levels of LDL and cholesterol significantly dropped.

- In comparison to healthy rats, genistein treatment decreased the level of TNF- α .
 - Genistein reduced the number of cysts & increased healthy follicles & corpora lutea.
4. **Yue Huang and Xiang Zhang, 2021⁽⁴⁹⁾: Luteolin** (Phytoestrogen) pre-clinical study in the dose of [25, 50 & 100 mg/kg] resulting
- Luteolin normalised the estrus cycle.
 - The weight and width of the ovary were reduced.
 - Treatment in PCOS rats reduced corpus luteum loss as well as polycystic oocyte
 - Significantly reduced LH and testosterone levels while increased FSH and estradiol levels.
 - Demonstrated reduction of insulin resistance by activating the PI3K/AKT signalling pathway.
 - Showed increased level of GSH and reulated the reduced activities of SOD, CAT & GSH-Px.
 - Nrf2 signalling in rats with PCOS were increased.
5. **Yanyuan Zhou et al, 2021⁽⁵⁰⁾: Proanthocyanidins** pre-clinical study in the dose of [50 & 150 mg/kg] for 21 days resulting
- In rats with PCOS, BW & relative ovarian weight significantly decreased after PC treatment.
 - The serum T, LH & LH/FSH levels in the PCOS group were decreased.
 - In PCOS rats, PC treatment significantly elevated the antioxidant enzymes like Cat, Sod2, Gpx3, Mgst1, Gsta4, Sod1 & Prdx.
 - PCs significantly reduced TGF-R1, p-Smad3, p-Smad2 & Smad4 levels & regulated the downregulation of Smad7.
6. **Sanaz Alaei et al, 2022⁽⁵¹⁾: Thymoquinone** pre-clinical study in the dose of [5 & 10 mg/kg] every 3 days for 30 days resulting
- Showed increased number of corpus luteum, GPx1 gene expression in ovaries, number of unilaminar, multilaminar, antral & graffian follicles & level of FSH in the blood when compared to untreated PCOS.
 - Ovaries in the thymoquinone groups had significantly fewer atretic follicles, ovarian weight & volume, volume density of cortex, ovarian cysts, expression of Bax gene, Bax/Bcl2 ratio, levels of LH, LH/FSH ratio & T in the blood.

7. **Bushra Hassan Marouf,2022⁽⁵²⁾: Silibinin** pre-clinical study in the dose of [100 & 200 mg/kg] for 19 days resulting
 - Reduction of BW & regulated estrus cyclicity.
 - The weight of abdominal fat decreased in the silibinin groups & drop in the HD-200 group was statistically significant.
 - Silibinin relieved insulin resistance in PCOS rats and demonstrated lower glucose rise in OGTT study.
 - After treatment, lipid profile & insulin level both decreased but not statistically significant.
8. **Yasmine F. Ibrahim a et al, 2022⁽⁵³⁾: Diacerein** pre-clinical study in the dose of [25 & 50 mg/kg] for 14 days resulting
 - The DIA significantly lowered higher BW, ovarian weight along with ovarian size & cyst levels and also elevated serum T, LH, insulin & lipid profile.
 - By lowering the elevated levels of MDA & total nitrite & raising the suppressed levels of SOD & CAT, DIA demonstrated prevention of the oxidative stress in the ovaries, liver & muscles.
 - DIA increased the concentrations of the protective proteins like Keap-1, Nrf2 & OH-1.
 - DIA inhibited the upregulated inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, TNF-, & the IL-1/NF-B signalling pathway, as well as the increased mRNA level of NLRP3 and caspase-1.
9. **Azmath Farhana et al, 2022⁽⁵⁴⁾: Anacardic acid(AA)** pre-clinical study in the dose of [10 and 40 mg/kg] for 15 days resulting
 - Compared to PCOS group, AA showed decreased body weight, increased uterine weight, and ovary weight.
 - Produced the best improvement in the changed lipid profile and also reversed the hormonal irregularity.
 - Exhibited higher serum levels of SOD and CAT in comparison to PCOS group.
 - Healthy follicles, healthy stroma, normal granulosa and theca cells were observed.
10. **Mohd Zahoor ul haq Shah et al, 2022⁽⁵⁵⁾: Gallic acid** pre-clinical study in the dose of [75 mg/kg] for 60 days resulting
 - Showed reduced levels of inflammatory cytokines, blood sugar, serum insulin, testosterone, LH, and the LH/FSH ratio.
 - Showed increased level of oestrogen, oxidative capability and enzyme activity.

- The mRNA expression level of CYP11a1, CYP19a1, KITL, PTGS2 and Adipo R1 were elevated.
11. **Yan-Xiang Wu et al, 2022⁽⁵⁶⁾: Naringenin** (Phytoestrogen) pre-clinical study in the dose of [20 mg/kg] resulting
- Demonstrated a significant decrease in body weight, improved hormone levels, reduced insulin resistance, and attenuated harmful ovarian tissue alterations.
 - Increased PGC-1, SIRT1, occluding, and claudin-1 expression in the colon.
 - Prevotella and Gemella were also shown to be down-regulated, but Butyricimonas, Lachnospira, Parabacteroides, Butyricococcus, Streptococcus, and Coprococcus were found to be up-regulated.
12. **Zhi Li et al,2022⁽⁵⁷⁾: Liquiritin** pre-clinical study in the dose of [20 mg/kg] for 21 days resulting
- Showed better insulin sensitivity and lowered fasting blood sugar levels.
 - Lowered the amounts of testosterone and dehydroepiandrosterone sulphate in serum.
 - Less cystic dilated follicles were seen in the liquiritin group's ovaries than in the PCOS group's during histomorphological examination of the ovaries.
 - Reduced mRNA expression of Cyp17a1, Cyp19a1, Fshr, Hsd3b2, Runx2, and Ccn2.

Discussion

The hormonal issue called PCOS results in enlarged ovaries and tiny cysts. Although exact aetiology of polycystic ovarian syndrome is in question, environmental and genetic factors may both contribute to it. Several symptomatic treatments such as Metformin, Clomiphene citrate, and statins are available for PCOS. These drugs are only responsible to manage insulin resistance, obesity, and hormonal imbalance, rather than directly addressing the condition. As opposed to conventional treatments for PCOS, which have been linked to side effects such as lactic acidosis, hot flashes, and psychological disorders, herbal remedies for PCOS must be employed that have a direct effect on the condition without any negative side effects. We discussed 32 herbal compounds and phytoconstituents that were investigated in 2021–2022 in this review. A few of them function as phytoestrogens like bitter melon (*Momordica charantia* L.), aloe vera, turmeric, piper longum, and Korean red ginseng and so on. Phytoestrogens are a class of analogues generated from plants that work like mammalian oestrogen; they physically and functionally bind to oestrogen receptors, trigger the formation of SHBG in the liver, and have an impact on the metabolism of sexual hormones. Estrogens have an impact on both the human and animal reproductive systems. By boosting ovulation rates and lowering ovarian follicle atresia, phytoestrogens control steroidogenesis. Additionally, it promotes folliculogenesis⁽⁵⁸⁾ This study explains benefits of different herbal plants and phytoconstituents in treatment of PCOS. Herbal treatment with plants and its phytoconstituents responsible for regulation of estrous cycle, lipid and hormonal level along with increasing insulin sensitivity in letrozole induced polycystic ovarian syndrome. For eg. Ali et al, conducted a study on PCOS utilising *Cicer arietinum* L. and discovered a decrease

in ovarian weight as well as a decrease in the number and size of cystic follicles and also increase granulosa cell thickness and a decrease in theca cell thickness. Also showed improved Hormonal, metabolic, and antioxidant status. Cyp11a1 mRNA expression significantly decreased which is more prevalent in polycystic ovarian syndrome theca cells than in normal cells. Turmeric extract is another example, as demonstrated by Shah and Shrivastava. They noticed a weight drop in the body, reverted the hormonal irregularity and best improvement in the altered profile of lipid. In letrozole-induced PCOS rats, treatment with turmeric extract reduces plasma IL levels and raises the level of circulating adiponectin. Significantly boosted SOD and GSH activity and MDA. In this study, several herbal components produced a variety of results. So, it is vital to categorise herbal compounds in accordance with changes in gene expression levels, hormonal and neurological factors, and other factors. They regulate hormones that affect the neurological system and its main axis in reproductive system consisting of testosterone, oestrogen, LH and FSH, a number of herbal chemicals and substances deserve closer attention.^{(59) (60)}

In addition to the advantages of their nutritional content and their potential for the identification of novel pharmacological molecules, plants are a rich source of phytonutrients with positive health effects. Although the specific mechanisms by which phytonutrients work are still not fully understood, they are crucial for maintaining human health. A diet high in phytonutrients may help prevent conditions associated with age such cancer, heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and neurological diseases, according to epidemiological research⁽⁶¹⁾

Now a days, various marketed herbal preparations are available to regulate the estrous cycle in women due to easy availability and affordability. PCOS can be treated with non-chemical and herbal components by figuring out the precise reason of the condition and its molecular base. To demonstrate the efficacy of these natural compounds for the treatment of PCOS, additional pre-clinical, clinical and experimental investigations are required. Numerous

commercialised products are available, including Gynoveda capsules, Shree Baidyanath Ayurved, Shatavari {join lifesciences Pvt. Ltd.}, Herbo natural {Herbo natural Pvt. Ltd.}, and Nuskhe {Paras} capsules, Dr. Vaidya's {Herbolab India Pvt. Ltd.} capsules, Dabur Lodhrasav {Dabur India Ltd.}, Ayurveda 24 {Trade India} which contain a variety of herbal compounds, including Methi, Neem, Manjistha, Shatavari, Amla, Ashwagandha, Flax seeds that can help to regulate cysts, lower insulin resistance, balance hormones, stabilise endocrine glands and the brain system⁽⁶²⁾. All the mentioned phytoconstituents and herbal compounds in this review will be useful in future for the development of a novel polyherbal formulation that can lower the risk of PCOS.

Conclusion

According to this review, herbal extracts and phytoconstituents produce reduction in insulin resistance, hyperandrogenism and weight of ovary along with increase in ovulation. Therefore these plants and phytoconstituents can be somewhat effective in this condition, providing an opportunity in future to investigate and discover novel herbal formulation.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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